

Best Practices
Report
Labour market
integration of
third-country nationals in Croatia, the
Czech Republic, Hungary and
Slovakia

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Introduction

This document consists of a series of 15 best practices successfully implemented in the Career Path project partner countries (Croatia, Slovakia, Hungary, Slovenia). Best practices document professional opportunities and career guidance provided to migrants. They include the cases when migrants are getting good support in their career growth which can serve as examples to be replicated elsewhere.” Best practices are put together as a spin off from the interviews and by contacting additional service providers.

Each example of good practice is presented in a clear and concise manner in order to be easily implemented in a new context. It includes information on institution that developed a good practice, target groups, detailed description of activity, expected benefits for target groups, resources required to implement a good practice as well as justification for its further usage. Since the collected best practices were developed in different countries and by various types of institutions (public, private, NGOs etc.) information of transferability (possibility of using it in different country/institutional contexts) is also provided. Finally, reader can also rely on provided websites and other references to get more information on a given good integration solution.

Best Practice: Mentoring / Mentor-Állás

Partner name: Menedék Association For Migrants

Name and position of the respondent: Barcza Ildikó (project manager of the project)

Date of the interview: November, 2020

References or documentation about the best practice:
<https://menedek.hu/en/node/639>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): employment of TCNs, awareness education of employers

Target group(s): Employers, HR professionals, vulnerable Third Country Nationals

Financial background: Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) MMIA-2.2.6/3-2015-00001

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): 2016-2018

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INTEGRATION OF
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IN CROATIA, THE
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HUNGARY AND
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DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

For more than 25 years, Menedék has been helping foreigners living in Hungary to find a job and integrate into the labor market within various projects. However, in July 2016, a special program focusing on this purpose was started to help disadvantaged third-country nationals, especially those enjoying international protection, to find a job and remain stable in the labor market.

Refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection in Hungary are entitled to almost entirely the same rights as Hungarian citizens. Still, people in need of international protection have limited access to state provided social, education and health care services and limited opportunities to find steady employment in the labour market. They face various challenges such as lack of Hungarian language knowledge and competence, lack of supporting social connections, too little knowledge about local customs and bureaucratic processes and the hostile, xenophobic attitude of the host society.

The goal of this project was to raise the employment opportunities of vulnerable, underprivileged third-country nationals - especially those of beneficiaries of international protection - and to help them to remain on the labour market. Successful applications and permanent employment are achieved by providing complex support

both to the job seekers and the employers as well, and empowering the target group for success in the future in the job market.

Detailed description:

In cooperation with third-country national jobseekers and Hungarian employers, in this project the focus was on empowering both the jobseekers and the employers. The goal was to help the effective intercultural communication and the management of intercultural conflicts.

Intercultural encountering in work places may result in misunderstandings and conflicts for both parties (employer, employee). It is important to know that often the backgrounds of these misunderstandings are various cultural patterns, norms, and behavioral differences, strange or not known to a person from another culture. It is worth paying attention to these situations, to recognize them and to understand them.

Work with job seekers: In addition to various job-search and job-finding activities, special attention was paid to job-seekers to prepare for the intercultural challenges they face in a workplace.

Working with employers: An information leaflet was prepared for employers who are planning to employ third-country nationals. Various facts were included that are useful to employers, to give an insight into the work-related issues typical of third-country nationals working in Hungary, to summarize the legal regulations on their employment, to share employer experiences and practical advice to employ them.

In addition to the publication, personal discussions took place arising from the employment and cooperation of third-country nationals, paying special attention to issues of intercultural communication and conflict management. If co-operation was needed, there was a mediation between the employer and the employee.

The work was assisted by intercultural mediators who have an especially important role in the interpretation of these situations towards both parties.

Part of our project was a communication campaign called "This is how we work" targeting the employers.

With help of our services the candidates could apply easier for their desired positions, discover new opportunities, set their professional goals, widen their skills and knowledge necessary for employment and improve their mental health:

- social counselling and mentoring
- legal counselling

- mental health support in form of private sessions
- alternative group therapy sessions
- job hunter club
- occupational group therapy
- internship programmes to achieve work experience
- tutoring and competence development in Hungarian

Employers could chose from the following services:

- recruitment of candidates, assistance in establishing contact
- social and legal counselling, professional mentoring
- a community to exchange professional experiences
- an info brochure about employing third-country nationals

All the above services were provided by a team of qualified experts: professional social workers, legal counsellor, psychologist and intercultural mediator contribute to our work. The project was supported by volunteers.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

TCNs were empowered in the job seeking and often got employed in the project. Employers were prepared to employ TCNs, and their cooperation was followed by the project.

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

A team of qualified experts provided the services: professional social workers, legal counselor, psychologist and intercultural mediator contribute to our work. Volunteers supported the project.

Why is it the best practice?

The complexity of the project resulted in empowering two sides, the employers and the TCN employees. In this way not only TCNs got employed with the help of the project, but we were empowering them in job seeking and also the employers in how to employ TNCs in the future.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

The leaflet for the employers can be adapted to any country involved. https://menedek.hu/sites/default/files/media/document/2018/05/22/igydolgozunkmi-final_eng_web.pdf

Best Practice: MIraGE – Migrant Integration for Growth in Europe

Partner name: Menedék Association For Migrants

Name and position of the respondent: Borbála Takács, project manager

Date of the interview: November, 2020

The institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner): Subjective Values Foundation

References or documentation about the best practice:

<https://www.mirageproject.eu/en/mirage-home/>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): MIraGE works to increase the swift access and integration of third-country nationals into the labor market of their European host countries.

Target group(s): Third-country nationals, Host country employers

Financial background: The project was funded by the European Union's Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): 2018 -2021

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DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

Subjective Values Foundation, a non-profit organization founded in 2002 that aims to tackle racism and discrimination by supporting ongoing dialogue between cultures. Moreover, the foundation aims to create a sustainable society, to promote European ideals in Hungary and to provide a platform for young individuals to identify and transfer those values and ideas which play an important role in their life. MIraGE works to increase the swift access and integration of third-country nationals into the labor market of their European host countries. The project is run by 12 partners from 8 European countries (Bulgaria, Sweden, Italy, France, Austria, Cyprus, Romania, Hungary)

Detailed description:

Despite the great potential that migrants can represent for European economies, there are several issues that must be addressed. In all Member States, some employers appreciate the potential of TCNs while others tend not to engage with the foreign laborers due to a lack of information regarding their employability, their skills, and the legal procedures which must be followed in order to recruit them.

At the same time, migrants are not fully aware of the many professional opportunities available to them, or how to access them. This is especially true of self-employment in host countries.

In other countries, the legal framework, policy decision-making, and insufficient language skills of the third-country nationals significantly impede their integration into the labor market.

In light of this, the MIraGE consortium implements the following different actions to increase the access of third-country nationals to the European labor markets and to foster integration: Mapping the employers' needs and attitudes by carrying out an online survey, Conduct interviews to explore good practices

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

- Using the results of the research, creating a handbook for employers and publishing it in 9 EU languages
- Developing two different country-specific training programs, both for TCNs and employer
- Promoting activities and best practices, creating a promo video, and running a social media campaign
- Collecting feedback so that the results can be transferred to future projects
- Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):
- A team of qualified experts doing the research and providing trainings
- Create promo video
- Social media campaign
- Employers survey

Why is it the best practice?

The project in Hungary has two distinct elements that makes it a best practice. On the one hand to inform possible employers about the steps on how to employ TCNs, and on the other to train TCNs who already obtain a work permit, about the local legal frameworks and practical steps to start their own enterprises.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

During the project, the partners have collected and published a handbook to present best practices implemented in different social, economic, and legislative contexts, all with the same objective: to promote the professional inclusion of employed and self-employed TCNs. Besides, during the project, the partners will create specific training programs both for TCNs and employers that will be published in 9 EU languages.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

The project is still in progress, therefore elements that are impossible to transfer to another context are not yet visible.

Best Practice: Jövőkerék

Partner name: Menedék Association For Migrants

Name of the best practice: Labor market services for immigrant women

Name and position of the respondent: Attila Mészáros, project coordinator

Date of the interview: November, 2020

The institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner):

Jövőkerék Alapítvány (Wheel of Future Public Utility Foundation)

References or documentation about the best practice:
<http://jovokerek.hu/noi-projekt/>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): labour market services, migrant women

Target group(s): Third Country National women

Financial background: The project was funded by the European Union's Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): 2014-2015

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DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The goal of the Jövőkerék Alapítvány (Wheel of Future Public Utility Foundation) is to promote and support local communities, non-governmental organizations and autonomous citizens as well as independent initiatives and programs promoting the development of strengthening and enforcing European values. The foundation wants to help civil society partners to mature their various ideas into concrete development projects and to implement them. In doing so, the foundation would like to place great emphasis on the methods and tools of understanding, thinking together, and cooperating, as well as open communication and information exchange.

Detailed description:

The project, which provides a complex package of services, consisted of the following elements and mutually reinforcing activities:

The social mentor of the project was helping to solve housing, social, and other issues, while the participants were able to find solutions to problematic issues and difficult life situations that may have hindered successful integration. During the job search group sessions, the participants got general and special information about the labor market, the conditions in Hungary, the successful methods and techniques of job search, and the labor market situation in Hungary that affects them.

Job search mentoring is a complex form of individual assistance. The consultant and the individual clients jointly mapped the client's abilities and possibilities and explored the obstacles. They agreed on the goals to be achieved during the training and performed the necessary tasks. The consultants carried out a competency measurement to examine the progress and satisfaction of the clients. In addition, weekly job search club events were organized with the aim to help the placement by providing information, developing job search skills, and mental support.

The package also included assertive training which aimed at achieving equal opportunities for women, strengthening their advocacy capacity, and supporting their own initiatives, improving the quality of their relationships, reducing communication and conflict management difficulties. These trainings also included both film and drama sessions as well as elements of yoga.

The legal advice package aimed to address legal issues that arose during the project. It sought solutions to different kinds of bureaucratic problems (administration, the legal background to starting a business, borrowing, family and social affairs, settlement matters, etc.). The goal was to explore the legal problems of the users and to answer them as widely as possible by providing advice and drafting official documents.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

- To empower TCNs in the job seeking and often get employed in the project.
- To provide TCNs help to find solutions to problematic issues and difficult life situations
- To support TCNs with legal advice for different bureaucratic problems

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

A team of qualified experts provides services including job search training, individual counseling, legal support for different bureaucratic problems.

Why is it the best practice?

Feedbacks received from the participant TCNs were very positive. They have received individual counselling and personalized information about their opportunities, job search, work methods, and work-culture that may differ from their own culture. They learn and practice methods that help self-assertion, cooperation, and conflict resolution. During the weekly job search club participants had the possibility to share their experiences, give advice, and empower each other.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

The project was the Foundation's first initiative that addressed job-seeking TCN women's needs in Hungary/ Budapest. Its methodological guide was later transferred to future projects within the organization. The general design of the project could be transferable to other international contexts if it is tailored to the local needs community demands are considered.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

The project was designed to fit the Hungarian context. The legal support package was strongly fitted to the Hungarian policy environment which may alter in every country. Also, the job searching club was designed to get insights into what are TCNs possibilities in the Hungarian job market.

Best Practice: COMIN project

Partner name: Mareena

Name of the best practice: Mareena and COMIN project – “Creation of a Community Center for Work and Knowledge Mobility in Nitra”
Name of specific activity: Free Slovak language courses associated with intercultural learning in Nitra (Slovakia)

Name and position of the respondent: Viera Orichová, Lawyer and Legal Advice Consultant of First Contact Services, “COMIN project - Creation of a Community Center for Work and Knowledge Mobility in Nitra”; Miriama Bošelová, Local Coordinator of the Volunteer, Community and Educational programme in Nitra, Mareena.

Date of the interview: October, 2020

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner): Mareena and the Nitra Community Foundation

References or documentation about the best practice:

- Project main page: <https://comin.sk/en/>
- Information about Free Slovak language courses associated with intercultural learning in Nitra:
<https://comin.sk/en/services/language-intercultural-courses-for-foreigners/>

Field of the best practice: Educational/Professional Development (language and skill courses)

Target group(s):

In addition to foreigners, the target group of the COMIN's counselling service are the citizens of the city of Nitra, who needed to obtain more information and solve problems in connection with migrants living in the city. Their counselling services were also used by employers. The target groups of Free Slovak language courses associated with intercultural learning in Nitra are foreigners.

Financial background:

The implementation of free language courses in Nitra was part of Mareena's cooperation with The Nitra Community Foundation in the form of the COMIN project. The project is supported by the ACF - Slovakia program, which is funded by the EEA Financial Mechanism 2014-2021. The administrator of the program is the Slovak Ekopolis Foundation in partnership with the Open Society Foundation (Slovakia - Bratislava) and the Carpathian Foundation. The project is co-financed by a grant from the City of Nitra.

Thanks to the financial support, the courses were free for participants (for TNCs and citizens of EU member states with temporary or permanent residence in the Slovak Republic).

Dates of the best practice (if applicable):

The whole “COMIN project - Creation of a Community Center for Work and Knowledge Mobility in Nitra” lasted from July 2019 to December 2020.

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The main goal of the COMIN project is to create services for social inclusion of migrants - TNCs and citizens of EU member states with temporary or permanent residence in Nitra (Slovakia) - with the aim of helping overcome barriers between citizens and migrants, and reducing xenophobia in the community. Another goal was to create a local strategy for the City of Nitra based on the cooperation of key players affected by the topic of social inclusion - the City of Nitra, employers, the non-governmental sector, representatives of the foreign police, the employment office, and active representatives of migrants. The strategy meant to define comprehensive solutions needed to achieve the social inclusion of migrants, overcome barriers to coexistence, and combat xenophobia in the community.

The main goal of this cooperation was to improve the situation of refugees and migrants through the provision of courses and professional development opportunities. Slovak language courses are provided free of charge to TCNs (refugees and migrant workers). With an increased interest in courses the program also accepted EU citizens. However, third-country nationals, and in particular refugees, remain the primary target group. An advantage of including both EU and third-country nationals was the enrichment of the program with different experiences, skills, and culture. This dimension added new dynamism to the course.

Mapping the needs:

In general, there is a lack of affordable language courses for low-income foreigners in Slovakia. The only organization that offers open Slovak language courses in Slovakia for citizens from outside the EU is the IOM Migration information center (in Bratislava and Košice). In Nitra, Mareena, in cooperation with Nitra Community Foundation, organizes Slovak language courses as the first and only free option. Courses are aimed at Slovak language conversation,

and thus provide an additional skill even for those attending regular language school. The course itself has been very popular among foreigners living in Nitra.

Detailed description:

Based on experience with managing Slovak language courses in Bratislava, Mareena was invited to cooperate with the Nitra Community Foundation to organize Slovak language courses for foreigners living in or nearby the city of Nitra. As Mareena has a Regional Coordinator in Nitra, the organization of courses in Nitra was smooth. Mareena implemented the same system of course organization as used in Bratislava. Mareena managed a Slovak language course for people with special needs (people who do not know the latin alphabet, people with limited literacy, people who can only speak their own mother language) as well as a Slovak language course for pre-intermediate.

Based on previous experience, Mareena organized courses two times per year (12-week or 10-week long semesters). In Autumn 2019, one course for beginners took place twice a week for 60 minutes, for a period of 10 weeks and was very popular among students (opportunities to study Slovak in Nitra are limited), who not only improved their language skills, but also found new social connections in Nitra. As interest in the Slovak language course in Nitra increased, Mareena decided to organize courses for beginners and pre-intermediates during the spring semester of 2020. Due to the Covid-19 outbreak, which hit Slovakia in the beginning of March 2020, Mareena continued with online courses via Zoom. Students appreciated the opportunity to learn the language even during the pandemic. For some students, it was also a way of preventing social isolation. In Autumn 2020, another online course for beginners was organized. While courses are generally aimed at Slovak language conversation, they also provide additional skills on social and cultural orientation in the city, as well as presentation.

Mareena goes through the following processes during the organization and implementation of the course: setting a topic that is based directly on the needs of clients; selection of lecturers; recruitment of participants (online registration, active promotion online and offline; promotion through cooperating organizations and through relevant branches of the foreign police); enrollment in the course (all registrants are invited to enroll, which consists of a written test and an oral interview with lecturers); feedback during the course (systematic documentation through the class book, attendance records, timetable); the evaluation process and statistical evaluation after the course (feedback from participants; feedback from lecturers focusing on their level of satisfaction with cooperation,

communication, and the meeting of expectations); an evaluation meeting with lecturers (one evaluation meeting per type of language course per semester, aimed at ideas and improvements for next semester).

In the process of organizing Slovak language courses, an opportunity to provide language courses for companies on a commercial basis developed which will be explored in the future.

Organizing language courses also presents several challenges: 1) Looking for or hiring lecturers (there are several reasons, but mainly related to the lack of experts in the topic; the offered working hours in a small number of hours during the week; quite challenging to replace lecturers who decided to end their cooperation between semesters); 2) Lack of a comprehensive methodology for Slovak language courses (although Mareena's Slovak language lecturers undergo a didactic preparation with an expert from the local university and use formal textbooks, each lecturer is free to prepare for the class in their own way, using the materials and books they prefer. The lack of a comprehensive methodology was a significant hindrance for the online courses. Mareena tried to solve this problem with experts from the Slovak center focused on teaching Slovak to foreigners [Studia Academica Slovaca], who prepared Sillabi for both Slovak courses [beginner and pre-intermediate], sillabi are in the testing phase); 3) Number of participants in each lesson (it has been hard to predict how many participants would attend each course lesson, because some clients did not come regularly and this was particularly challenging for lecturers who had to be prepared for more improvised lessons with learning activities requiring a different ad hoc number of participants); 4) The dropping number of course participants (Mareena usually had a good number of participants at the beginning of each semester, but the number of participants generally dropped after the first few lessons. One way to solve this situation could be to prepare a reserve list of students for every course so that when a free spot opens, it is possible to fill it immediately with another student).

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

Course manager; local coordinator; in the case of low-cost / free-of-charge courses, a project with a financial budget to cover course costs; cooperation within organizations working with foreigners; cooperation with experts in the field of foreigner education; language course teachers.

Why is it the best practice?:

- The Comin project is unique in Slovakia. The establishment of The Point of First Contact is a very positive effort to establish communication between foreigners and the municipal government. This contact creates opportunities for foreigners to have a secure space where they receive all necessary information, in a language they understand. The people employed in this department have good expertise in the legislation concerning foreigners and an overview of the services available to them. In addition to service provision, the department enables good communication between foreigners and the city. The contact point is the first of its kind in Slovakia -- no other municipality has established such a department.
- The project worked with an already active non-governmental organization in the field of integration of foreigners. Direct Services were provided at the local level and in an area where Mareena already had previous experience. The implementation of the language courses was organizationally and professionally advanced. It included cooperation with experts in Slovak language instruction, as well as introductory didactic training for instructors. Enrollment in courses consisted of a written and oral examination, ensuring appropriate placements. The courses were also precisely documented (e.g., attendance, and class schedules). Additionally, instructors ensured the cultural competency of the curriculum by following a Code of Ethics and by taking into account sensitive issues related to intercultural differences.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?:

This best practice is largely transferable to contexts where NGOs and municipalities have productive partnerships. Importantly, such a programme may only be feasible in municipalities of a sufficient size. Size determines both the number of foreigners present to make use of language classes, and also the amount of resources the municipality has at its disposal.

Best Practice: The Career Guidance Programme for Foreigners Living in Slovakia

Partner name: Mareena

Name and position of the respondent: Katarína Levčíková,
Education and Professional Development Programme Manager,
Mareena

Date of the interview: November, 2020

References or documentation about the best practice:

1) Mareena - Career Guidance Programme:

<https://www.euroguidance.sk/nckp/mareena/>

2) Inclusive Third Sector - an example of good practice (about Mareena's Career Guidance Programme on page 6)

<http://tyzdenkariery.sk/wp-content/uploads/Pr%C3%ADru%C4%8Dka-TK2020.pdf>

3) Interview with programme manager, Katarína Levčíková, about Mareena's Career Guidance Programme:

<https://rozvojkariery.sk/pomoc-s-uplatnenim-pre-cudzincov-uz-aj-na-slovensku/>

4) The National Career Guidance Awards 2019:

<https://www.euroguidance.eu/the-national-career-guidance-awards-2019>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Personal and Career Development

Target group(s): Third-country nationals residing in Slovakia, who are seeking employment or wish to change jobs/retrain.

Financial background: The program was funded through the Porticus grant scheme, Porticus Grant title: Integration of refugees and migrants into local communities - Slovak vital church communities engagement.

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): The grant was used in the implementation of the four project series from April 2018 to August 2020.

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The Career Guidance Programme of Mareena is organized in cooperation with professional career counsellors and aims to help people with international protection and foreigners who have difficulty finding employment in Slovakia. The main goal of the program is to strengthen economic and social independence, support clients in finding or changing jobs, strengthen presentation skills, and help them set realistic career goals and define their competencies.

After completing The Career Guidance Programme, graduates can enrol in The Mentoring Programme, which follows up on The Career Guidance Programme and connects expert volunteers from Slovakia with foreigners who want to fulfill their professional goals, change their career focus or start their own business.

Mapping the needs (if applicable):

Foreigners in Slovakia often have difficulty finding employment in their previous area of employment (in their home country) or continuing in their field of study. Primary obstacles include the language barrier, the recognition of diplomas, lack of self-confidence, and high employer expectations. These findings spurred the creation of the professional development programme. The programme focuses on providing foreign with useful information about the labour market in Slovakia, developing their soft skills, increasing their self-confidence, realizing their expectations and, ultimately, helping them apply for jobs.

To map specific needs: a questionnaire was sent to those interested in which they could record their preferences regarding the objectives, topics, and expectations of the programme, their previous experiences with career guidance, as well as their education and current employment status. Based on this information, the programme was then modified.

Detailed description:

The thematic areas of the programme were based on a preliminary screening of the needs of potential clients (online questionnaire), the experience of Mareena staff, and methodological materials created in the Erasmus+ Kaleidoscope of Competencies Project. In addition, Mareena was inspired by other European projects, such as the Erasmus+ project, ProfilPass, and the project Competence Cards.

All methodological materials were modified for actual participants. Based on pre-programme questionnaire and the experience of the lecturers, the programme ran as a combination of group and individual meetings. In group activities, mutual support of clients could be developed, which often proved to be crucial, as everyone was in various stages of the Slovak labour market and more experienced individuals could provide proven experience and information. The advantage of group meetings was also mutual feedback between the participants. Targeted feedback was specifically used to identify the strengths of participants and to practice job interviews. Individual meetings were mainly devoted to CV consultations, job interview preparation, or more detailed examinations of clients' work wishes and plans. The joint meetings consisted of shorter meetings on weekdays and longer meetings occurred over the weekend. Each series of the programme was adapted based on feedback from participants after the prior programme series ended. The Career Guidance Programme covers the following topics: (1) Introduction to the Programme (mapping participants' expectations, establishing group rules); (2) Strengths (participants explore their own strengths through feedback from others members of the programme, work with symbols and other experiential methods, and also what skills they would like to use, develop and offer in the labour market); (3) Values and competences (closely intertwined with 'Strengths' exploration of personal and work values); (4) Career Goal setting and action planning (use various interactive activities to plan real, feasible career step); (5) Labour market information, jobs portals and networking (providing practical information about the labour market in Slovakia, the most in-demand skills, the importance of, and ways to pursue, networking); (6) CV and cover letter (providing information on how to write an attractive CV and a cover letter tailored to specific advertised job positions); (7) Corporate environment and recruiting (particularly relevant for TCNs as large transnational corporations advertise numerous job vacancies that do not require knowledge of the Slovak language); (8) Self-presentation and presentation of plans (the last meetings in the program were devoted to self-presentation, e.g. career "speed-dating", practice job interviews, and presentation of plans for the next three months and a year).

Upon completing the programme, participants are offered the possibility of enrolling in a follow-up Mentoring Programme, which links third-country nationals, with Slovak professionals.

All series of the programme were led in English, though clients had the opportunity to express their preferences for Slovak or English before starting the programme. Communication in the group sometimes encountered a language barrier. However, an unplanned benefit of the program for some clients was an increase in their English competency and a strengthened willingness to use it actively.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

The Career Guidance Programme provides clients with the opportunity to learn about their strengths and weaknesses, improve their language skills, obtain information about the labour market in Slovakia, gain social contacts, and network. Participants especially appreciated individual meetings with career counsellors and information on professional development.

It is more challenging to measure the direct impact of the service on the professional and career development of graduates. Programme participants often continue with the Mentoring Programme, and Mareena tries to keep in touch with participants, in order to ascertain whether the Guidance Programme and Mentoring programme are effective (follow-ups occur after 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months). However, since many factors influence career and professional development, it is difficult to identify explicit impacts.

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

Human resources: (1) Education and Professional Development Program Manager responsible for recruiting participants, obtaining feedback, and organizing program instruction and the recruitment of career counsellors; (2) Well trained and qualified career counsellors ensure the effective implementation of the programme through knowledge of the relevant thematic areas, and experience working with clients.

Other conditions: (1) During the project, Mareena also became a member of The Slovak Association for Career Counselling and Career Development, gaining access to information about upcoming events on the topic of career counselling, as well as contacts for people who are professionally involved in the field; (2) If this activity is covered by projects (donors), this can ensure free / low cost services, increasing the size of the possible target group; (3) Within the educational and professional development programme, Mareena cooperated with additional organizations and employers, which helped with the promotion of the career counselling and mentoring programme.

Why is it the best practice?

We identified this programme as a Best Practice for three reasons:

- Within career counselling, specific programs for TCNs are rare. Thus, Mareena's program is unique, in that it involves

disadvantaged people in the Slovak labour market.

- The evaluation process for the programme was set up effectively and is not usually standard in similar programmes. The collection of feedback took place continuously after individual meetings and also after the end of the programme. Based on this information, the programme could be modified to better meet the needs of clients.

The evaluation of the programme had several levels: (1) Continuous evaluation (after each intensive meeting with the lecturers); (2) Final evaluation (at the conclusion of the programme, an online or offline questionnaire was administered that measured the satisfaction of participants; . these results were used to adjust the program to better suit the needs of clients) ; (3) Questionnaire evaluation with programme lecturers (evaluation of cooperation with Mareena, space for suggestions for improvements and changes in the program); (4) Comprehensive evaluation (questionnaire evaluations from course participants and lecturers were followed by an in-person evaluation meeting, where the lecturers and manager of the programme presented the results of the evaluations by participants, evaluated the mutual cooperation of lecturers with Mareena and also discussed new ideas, improvements and solutions to problems that arose).

- The use of a Code of Ethics was also specific to the programme. The Code of Ethics regulates the relationship between lecturers and clients, focusing on maintaining a professional approach, respecting clients and their cultural customs, and creating a safe space. When creating group rules, lecturers tried to take into account not only the basic rules for group work, but also the sensitive issue of intercultural difference. When this topic was opened during the meetings, they opened it directly and clarified in a mutual dialogue how some expressions are perceived by people from different cultures.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

The programme can be applied in any country, but it is very important to adapt the programme thematically to the labour market conditions of a given country and to connect with professionals in the field. Cooperation with experienced and qualified career counsellors is key for the programme. It is necessary to keep in mind that, even for career counsellors, it may be a new experience to work with TCNs, so it is necessary to prepare sufficient conditions for them to orientate themselves in the basic issues and specifics of working with this target group.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

The programme is adaptable and no significant limitations were identified.

Additional notes from the researcher:

The Career Guidance Programme in Mareena falls under the more comprehensive Professional Development Programme, which also includes a Mentoring Programme. Due to lack of space, we did not devote space to the Mentoring Programme in this report, but we consider it necessary to mention. The added value of this program is the possibility for graduates of The Career Guidance Programme to continue to fulfill their career goals with the help of an expert volunteer/mentor. Expert volunteers, successful professionals in various fields, mentor migrants in their professional and career development, help them fulfil their potential, provide guidance on the Slovak labor market and, ultimately, help foreigners craft successful career paths.

Best Practice: IOM Migration Information Centre (MIC)

We focused on two best practices at MIC:

1. Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries (TCNs);
2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers.

Name and position of the respondent: Veronika Marčanová, Senior Project Assistant, IOM Migration Information Centre (MIC)

Date of the interview: October, 2020; November, 2020

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner): International Organization for Migration (IOM) – Slovak Republic

References or documentation about the best practice:

Main website of IOM Migration Information Centre (MIC):

1. Various resources for TCNs and other foreigners: Legal, labour, social counseling ; support for education and retraining ; and courses on social and cultural orientation.

- <https://www.mic.iom.sk/en/>
- <https://iom.sk/en/activities/migrant-integration/iom-migration-information-centre.html>

2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers (only in Slovak language)

- [https://iom.sk/sk/aktivita/vzdelavanie-poradenske-sluzby/skolenia-a-poradenstvo-za](https://iom.sk/sk/aktivita/vzdelavanie-poradenske-sluzby/skolenia-a-poradenstvo-za-mestnavanie-cudzincov.html)
- [mestnavanie-cudzincov.html](https://iom.sk/sk/aktivita/vzdelavanie-poradenske-sluzby/skolenia-a-poradenstvo-za-mestnavanie-cudzincov.html)

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): employment counselling, education, retraining.

Target group(s): The primary target group of the first best practice is TCNs; for the second best practice, the target group is employers of foreigners in Slovakia.

Financial background:

1. Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries

Financially supported by the Ministry of the Interior of the Slovak Republic through projects from the EU Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) and the EU Internal Security Fund (Specific Objective SC2 INTEGRATION)

2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers

Paid service (service fully paid for by employers, without project or donor support).

Dates of the best practice (if applicable):

1. Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries

- from April 2006 to the present. As part of the description of the activity, we focused mainly on the year 2019.

2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers

- from January 2019 to the present.

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DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

IOM Migration Information Centre (MIC) is the counselling centre of the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in Slovakia, whose main objective is to provide services to foreigners in order to aid their integration in Slovakia (Free Advice and Services for Foreigners from Outside the EU). Since 2019, MIC also provides services to Slovak employers who are interested in employing foreigners from third countries. One of the main objectives of MIC is to improve the social and economic integration of foreigners through training and retraining. MIC is the first and, so far, only organization in Slovakia that provides comprehensive services to foreigners at one place. MIC services include legal, social and vocational counselling, retraining and further education, labor market inclusion, and the support of community life. The centre is primarily active in two Slovak cities - Bratislava and Kosice, but the centre carries out activities across all regions.

1. Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries

The main objective of employment counselling is to increase the professional capacities and job skills of TCNs through familiarization with the Slovak labor market, language and vocational training, and training/retraining programs. These efforts bolster the education, qualifications, and professional skills of TCNs, increasing their chances of entering the labor market, and promoting economic integration.

2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers

The main objective of educational and consulting services for Slovak employers is to provide practical training and counselling on the employment of foreigners from third, as well as EU, countries.

Mapping the needs (if applicable):

1. Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries

MIC tailors its employment counselling program based on its own work with clients and representatives of migrant communities. Through daily work with clients, feedback from service recipients, and through evaluative questionnaires of its activities, MIC identified several needs that the employment counselling program should address: (1) the need to increase awareness of the legal rights and obligations of foreigners living in the Slovak Republic; (2) the need to improve knowledge of institutions and their scope with regards to individual areas of life for foreigners in the Slovak Republic; (3) the need to improve Slovak language acquisition as well as cultural knowledge (e.g., customs) to aid social and economic integration; (4) the need to provide foreigners with better qualifications and training to increase their competitiveness in the labor market; and (5) the need to help foreigners navigate and overcome linguistic, legislative, and administrative barriers to integration and bureaucratic processes.

2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers

Between 2006 and 2018, MIC was contacted by a large number of employers who needed advice on legislative and practical issues related to the employment of foreigners, especially those from third countries. Seeing this demand, MIC (since January 2019) provides paid training and counselling for employers. Needs were identified on the basis of direct experiences with employers.

Detailed description:

1. Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries

MIC offers free counselling for foreigners from third countries in the following areas: labour market orientation; the job search process ; CV and cover letter preparation; preparation for a job interview; orientation in the recognition of diplomas and education; employment contracting advice; the rights and obligations of the employee and the employer; advice on loss of employment. From April 2006 to December 2019, 6 534 clients used employment counselling service. MIC also provides support for further education and retraining - it analyses the skills and qualifications of clients; provides information about studying in Slovakia, and assists them in finding suitable educational and retraining courses. MIC also provides its clients with the opportunity to obtain a financial contribution for education and retraining, under the condition that the course will help the client find a new job or improve their position at

their current job or business. The contribution can be used for training courses (such as a foreign language course, an accounting course, or a course in working with a PC) or retraining courses (such as a hairdressing course, or a course on working with a forklift.). Foreigners must provide a certificate and proof of payment. MIC also provides free group courses on strengthening "soft skills" like communication, self-presentation, or business skills.

2. Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers

MIC offers employers services related to the employment of foreigners from third countries (and, to a lesser extent, EU countries as well) in the form of group training. Between January 2019 and May 2020, MIC organized 13 group trainings, with 168 employees across 120 companies based in Slovakia. In these trainings, MIC connects expectations with practical and verified information, e.g. a step-by-step guide on arranging the residence and employment of a foreigner in Slovakia. In addition to group training, they also carry out "tailor-made training", which is directly adapted to the requirements of the employer and focuses on information that is relevant to their specific situation. In this case, the price of the service depends on the requirements of the employer (e.g., according to the number of participants or duration of training).

MIC also offers individual consulting services in the form of personal visits or consultations via e-mail or telephone (the price of the consultation is 80 euros without VAT / hour).

The most frequent consultation topics are: the employment of foreigners (visa and visa-free third-country nationals and foreigners from EU Member States; foreign students; or highly qualified foreigners on the basis of blue cards); navigating the acquisition of temporary residence and work permits (relevant legislation, residence and work permit step-by-step, deadlines and requirements for processing documents, the most common mistakes in the processing of permits, demonstrations of filling out the required forms, tips on other important sources of information).

As part of trainings and consultations, MIC also deals with topics such as the recognition of foreign education credentials; the procedure for family reunification with the employee's family members and their employment; the risks of illegal employment; and tips for integration measures and programs that will facilitate the integration of foreigners into both work and community life.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

The MIC employment counselling program has several benefits for third-country nationals: (1) effective integration into the labour market (the acquisition of work skills and economic independence); (2) language acquisition and social and cultural skills orientation on the labour market; (3) improvement of communication with employers, assistance in finding job offers or job placement; (4) sustained connection with personnel agencies and employers in individual regions of Slovakia; (5) expanded opportunities to acquire and supplement skills, education, and retraining; and (6) the independence of foreigners.

For employers, MIC consultations bring several tangible benefits: (1) providing employers with the capacity to hire TCNs without resorting to financially expensive relocation agencies; (2) the expansion of employer knowledge concerning the legal framework and practical process of hiring TCNs; (3) an increase in the cultural competency and relevant integration practices of Slovak employers.

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

The most important requirement of the programs are human resources. Both best practices require the knowledge of legal experts. Ideally, these experts would be graduates of the Faculty of Law and have several years of experience in providing legal advice to clients. They would also be oriented in legislation governing the residency of foreigners in Slovakia, as well as in various integration tools and policies. Experts should also be knowledgeable in English and other foreign languages, work with legal databases, and be familiar with processing recommendations from legal practice and legislative proposals in the areas of residency, integration, and migration. Further, it would be beneficial to have the employment counselling program be funded by third parties (e.g. donors or grants) in order to ensure a low cost, and thus accessibility. With project funding, these services could reach the largest possible target group.

Why is it the best practice?

MIC IOM has extensive and unique experience in providing practical assistance to migrants living in Slovakia. IOM has detailed first-hand knowledge of the experience and needs of migrants in the integration process, as well as information about the needs of employers. The presented best practices are based directly on the requirements and demand of these target groups.

At the same time, IOM's position as an intergovernmental organization in the field of migration renders it able to comment on Slovak laws relevant to integration and migration. Thus, IOM has the opportunity to inform lawmakers about key findings of projects and activities and to promote conclusions and recommendations within the legislative framework.

Finally, the counselling services offered to employers are unique. Given the complex system of laws and regulations concerning the employment of foreigners in Slovakia, employers may avoid doing so. This service helps companies and firms overcome this barrier, while also helping them learn best practice when it comes to the integration of foreigners already working in Slovakia.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

Both activities (Employment counselling for foreigners from third countries and Educational and consulting services for Slovak employers) are adaptable and no significant limitations were identified during the research. If transferring activities to another country, the activities need to be adapted to the specific legislative and legal framework of that country.

Best Practice: LUSH “All are welcome”

Partner name: Centre for Peace Studies

Name of the best practice: LUSH as part of their “All are welcome” Initiative

Name and position of the respondent: Ivona Barun, Human resources department manager.

Date of the interview: November 2020.

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner):

LUSH manufaktura d.o.o. is part of UK brand LUSH Fresh Handmade Cosmetics that operates in 48 countries across the globe with 7 production facilities. One of them is LUSH manufaktura d.o.o. in Croatia being established back in 2005.

References or documentation about the best practice:

Since this is internal employment policy there is no publicly available documentation and data.

Field of the best practice: Employment of third-country nationals, promotion of diversity and inclusion in work-force.

Target group(s): Third-country nationals (future employees), current employees.

Financial background: There are no specific financial contributions to this particular cause because this is an overall employment policy. Nevertheless, LUSH is planning on organising training “Interculturality – competence for present future” that will target leadership teams. This training will be provided by specialized external organisations.

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): This is an ongoing practice.

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

Objective of current employment policy is to support third-country nationals due to company policy that recognizes the importance of diversity and inclusion. strives to build a brand that represents the people of the world looking to expand perspectives and voices and shape our future. Through this initiative, they opened doors for the employment of third-country nationals.

“We believe in freedom of movement and that every person should have a right to choose where to live. The inclusion of third-country nationals is therefore just a manifestation of our core beliefs. Respect, cooperation, mutual understanding and promoting the culture of diversity and inclusion is of high importance in LUSH and living those values, implementing them in our work and actions is the main goal.”

Mapping the needs (if applicable):

There was no assessment of needs conducted before the implementation of this policy. However, with its internal policies, LUSH responds to social issues and strives to make a social impact, within the company and society.

Detailed description:

LUSH manufaktura d.o.o. is part of UK brand LUSH Fresh Handmade Cosmetics that operates in 48 countries across the globe with 7 production facilities. One of them is LUSH manufaktura d.o.o. in Croatia being established back in 2005. LUSH manufaktura d.o.o. is located in the area of Sveta Nedelja and Stupnik, operating in 5 premises and employing around 300 employees. According to its revenue and number of employees the company is the biggest cosmetic company in Croatia supplying fresh and handmade cosmetics to LUSH stores in 12 countries across Europe.

They believe people should be happy in their workplaces, that all employees should be treated in a fair manner and have the opportunity to develop themselves in a respectful and supportive environment. To them, it makes no difference where a person comes from and what their background is, so every applicant has a fair chance in the recruitment process. They employ people who have the will to work, benevolence, and team skills necessary to become a part of our team. LUSH has excellent experience employing third-country nationals. Third-country nationals often speak English and Croatian, so they can easily communicate and cooperate with other employees and offer them valuable experience working for LUSH. This year (2020) LUSH had 26 applicants from third countries, all of them were contacted and invited for an interview. Eight of them were employed originating from Peru, Syria, Senegal, Iraq, Brazil, India, Kosovo, Montenegro. Other 18 applicants from third countries mostly came from Bangladesh, Iraq, Egypt, Syria, Burundi, Philippines, Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In Croatian manufacturing the inclusion of the third-country nationals began in 2017 in collaboration with the Centre for Peace Studies

and Red Cross. At the time Croatia was facing a so-called “refugee crisis” and many refugees were transiting Croatia in the hope for a better life. As LUSH believes in the importance of freedom of movement this was the point where LUSH identified the need to get actively involved and implement their global “*All are welcome*” initiative. LUSH is building a brand that represents the people of the world looking to expand perspectives and voices to shape our future. In cooperation with the Centre for Peace Studies and Red Cross, LUSH spread the word about our job vacancies and got first applicants coming from Afghanistan, Ghana, Iraq, Syria etc. Although most of the jobs on offer are temporary seasonal jobs, LUSH is happy to share that one of these first 2017 recruits has stayed and is still a valued member of the team today.

Once they start working for LUSH, all employees go through so-called Induction Day where they are introduced to the LUSH history and LUSH values through a whole day training session. They are aware of the culture of inclusion even from the recruitment process, as it is highlighted in the recruitment presentation. Further promotion of diversity is also implemented in strategic programs, such as Respect at work training sessions, Diversity and Inclusion training for management. The LUSH UK created video and reading materials that have been introduced to their employees and it is a crucial part of their company policies – such as Respect at work policy. From June 2020 LUSH intensively started developing programs globally aiming to strengthen all our internal Diversity & Inclusion policies and practices. They originally kick-started with a 100-day plan covering many topics such as microaggressions in the workplace, discrimination etc. This extra work was started in response to the Black Lives Matters movement – when LUSH decided that there was more that needs to be done to ensure that all minorities that come to work at LUSH can have true equity and equality.

LUSH believes that a lot has been made to truly provide their third-country employees inclusive and positive working experience. We are looking forward to the results of the exit survey to detect areas for further development. Their 100-day Diversity and Inclusion plan put a renewed focus on all these issues and LUSH has made a worldwide company commitment to ensure ongoing continuous development on these issues, to ensure that they do not let complacency set in.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

Respect, cooperation, mutual understanding and promoting the culture of diversity and inclusion is of high importance in LUSH and living those values, implementing them in their work and actions is the main goal. By being open to employing third-country nationals, LUSH is directly removing barriers on the labour market and serves

as an example to other companies that might be hesitant in engaging and integrating third-country nationals within their work-force.

Material required/resources:

Several internal initiatives led to the successful integration of third-country nationals in work-force of LUSH:

- “All are welcome” Initiative
- Their 100-day Diversity and Inclusion

In addition to them, LUSH is planning on organising a training “Interculturality – competence for present future” that will target leadership teams. This training will be provided by specialized external organisations.

Why is it the best practice?

LUSH showed dedication in including third-country nationals into their work-force and is continuously working in removing barriers that third-country nationals might face once they become part of the company. Internal employment policies implemented by LUSH can serve as an example to other similar international and local companies and show the willingness of LUSH to recognise the power of diversity and inclusion. In their words:

“We believe in freedom of movement and that every person should have a right to choose where to live. The inclusion of third-country nationals is therefore just a manifestation of our core beliefs. Respect, cooperation, mutual understanding and promoting the culture of diversity and inclusion is of high importance in LUSH and living those values, implementing them in our work and actions is the main goal.”

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

This example of best practice is transferable to any context, and it is dependent on the internal employment policies and the willingness of companies to recognise the importance and added value of building a diverse working environment. Some resources should be allocated for training and addressing possible social issues that can reflect within the work-force as well.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to another context?

This example of best practice should be fully transferable.

Additional notes from the researcher:

It should be noted that within our interview the respondent identified one difficulty, the language barrier makes it harder to explain production processes and work tasks for those without English or Croatian language skills. So during the recruitment process, they find it important to select those candidates who have at least basic knowledge of English or Croatian language.

Best Practice: TrAZILica

Partner name: Centre for Peace Studies

Name of the best practice: TrAZILica - Social inclusion and strengthening the competitiveness of asylum seekers and migrants in the labour market in the Republic of Croatia

Name and position of the respondent: Dajana Ravlija, Social worker.

Date of the interview: November 2020.

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner): Jesuit Refugee Service Croatia implemented the project TrAZILica in cooperation with Public Open University Zagreb. Jesuit Refugee Service Croatia is a non-profit humanitarian organization whose mission is to accompany, serve and advocate the rights of refugees and other forcibly displaced persons. The association is part of the Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) international humanitarian organization founded in 1980.

References or documentation about the best practice: General information of the project TrAZILica can be found on [the webpage](#) of Jesuit Refugee Service Croatia. Furthermore, Croatian [media published a story](#) on refugees who went through this project.

- Official website of Jesuit Refugee Service containing information on project TrAZILica:
<http://www.jrs.hr/en/causes/trazilica-social-inclusion-and-strengthening-the-competitiveness-of-asylum-seekers-and-migrants-in-the-labor-market-in-the-republic-of-croatia/>
- Experience of participants of the project TrAZILica shared in Croatian newspaper *24sata*:
<https://www.24sata.hr/lifestyle/deportirali-su-ih-u-hrvatsku-isli-su-ponovo-u-skolu-rade-od-jutra-do-sutra-i-zele-ostati-kod-nas-718975>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Integration of third-country nationals into the labour market, employment of third-country nationals.

Target group(s): Third-country nationals, primarily refugees.

Financial background: This project was funded through the European Social Fund.

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): The project lasted 18 months, from March 2019 until September 2020.

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The main objective of the project was to contribute to increasing employability and competitiveness in the labour market and to improve the quality of life and social inclusion of asylum seekers and migrants in the Republic of Croatia. The activities of the project included around 50 asylum seekers and migrants, experts and about 20 volunteers focused on the preparation and implementation of tailored educational programs, Croatian language, social mentoring, development of soft skills of the target group and education of experts working on the project with the target group.

Mapping the needs (if applicable):

There was no mapping of the need's prior to the project implementation. However, Jesuit Refugee Service is an experienced NGO that is assisting asylum seekers and refugees in their process of integration and they are in a position to create and implement projects that can directly address the needs of asylum seekers and refugees.

Detailed description:

Jesuit Refugee Service Croatia is focused, among other things, on offering vocational training to asylum seekers and refugees through their projects, with the sole purpose of assuring that asylum seekers and refugees have access to educational programs that will give them a chance to acquire a new profession and rebuild their lives. Their project TraAZILica funded by the European Social Fund was successfully implemented in cooperation with the Public Open University Zagreb. The role of Jesuit Refugee Service within the project was to recruit asylum seekers and refugees who might be interested in enrolling in the language courses and the following educational programs. The process of recruitment was conducted by intercultural mediators working for the Jesuit Refugee Service, who also experienced being refugees in Croatia, and therefore had a network of people who needed assistance with their process of integration. Before every cycle of courses, Jesuit Refugee Service organised the so-called "motivational workshop" in which people had the option to choose for which profession they wish to enrol in an adequate educational program conducted by the Public Open University Zagreb. It is important to note that social workers working in Jesuit Refugee Service guided asylum seekers and refugees through all administrative and bureaucratic procedures.

Due to the comprehensive nature of the project, although it was first envisioned enrollment of 40, at the beginning 151 people applied. At the end of the project, 40 people went through language classes and educational programs, through which they gained basic knowledge of Croatian but also acquired new professions. Through this project, Jesuit Refugee Service strived to answer challenges that the national economy is facing, together with challenges shared by the asylum seekers and refugees. In the past few years, Croatia has been facing the so-called “exodus of young Croats”, essentially a larger movement of Croatian younger population to Western Europe. This immigration of Croatian younger population led to forming the gaps at the Croatian labour market, and Jesuit Refugee Service through their project TrAZILica wanted to educate asylum seekers and refugees following the current needs of the Croatian labour market, all with the purpose of fastening their process of integration. Most of the educational programs were focused on professions in tourism or IT, and by the end of the project, they added few other professions in the construction sector, due to a strong earthquake that hit Zagreb mid-March in 2020.

Projects such as TrAZILica allow almost an individual approach in the process of integrating asylum seekers and refugees into the labour market. Within 6 months asylum seekers and refugees managed to gain a new profession that was recognised by all relevant national institutions and helped them overcome barriers that previously existed when trying to enter into the Croatian labour market. The success of the project was dependent on the individual motivation of every project participants, and that is why continuous support from social workers working for Jesuit Refugee service was one of the crucial parts of the projects. People often forget that asylum seekers and refugees had already built their lives in their home countries and that every new beginning, such as the one offered through this project, acquires a lot of personal strength and motivation. Project evaluation showed that project participants were happy with the overall project and found it valuable to have access to intercultural mediators who together with social works provided guidance and support.

Jesuit Refugee Service emphasized the readiness of employers with whom they were in contact to employ asylum seekers and refugees who went through professional training and gained necessary skills. Employment of asylum seekers and refugees upon going through the project is the biggest success of TrAZILica.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

Project TrAZILica allowed asylum seekers and refugees to learn Croatian and gain additional skills through tailored education

programs, with the goal of filling out the gaps at the Croatian labour market.

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

This project was funded through the European Social Fund. To ensure its success and reach the project's objective it was necessary to gather well-skilled staff that continuously supported asylum seekers and refugees. Staff within the project offered support in learning the Croatian language, held educational programs and offered social mentoring. It is important to note the crucial role of intercultural mediators who motivated asylum seekers and refugees to go through the problem but also help them communicate needs that arose during the project implementation. They often had the role of personal counsellor and helped the social worker to follow-up on every project participant. The project funding ended in September 2019, and due to lack of resources project activities ended. However, Jesuit Refugee Service is implementing new projects that have the same objective as project TrAZILica.

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Why is it the best practice?

This is a comprehensive project that encompasses all stages important for successful integration into the labour market. Situational mapping analysis showed that language is often a barrier when integration into the labour market. This project addresses this issue in its first stage, through which project participants gain basic knowledge of Croatian. In addition to expanding the language skills, the project allowed participants to go through vocational training and to gain skills which will allow them to successfully integrate into the labour market. Furthermore, while conducting the project, Jesuit Refugee Service was continuously working with different employers, all to connect them with asylum seekers and refugees which could be part of their future work-force.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

Due to its funding nature, this project could be implemented in various EU states with slight changes according to different national contexts. The language barrier is an issue commonly shared, and without offering asylum seekers and refugees projects and programmes like this, the overall process of integration is lengthier. An important role in this project holds the Public Open University Zagreb that executed educational programs through which asylum seekers and refugees gained a new set of skills. For the success of

this project in another national context, it would be crucial for a non-governmental organisation to find a similar partner as the Public Open University Zagreb, due to this educational nature of the project itself. The Jesuit Refugee Service through this project actively worked on building a connection with possible employers which accelerated the process of asylum seekers and refugees finding employment.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to another context?

This example of best practice is transferable to any context.

Additional notes from the researcher:

The respondent informed us about the similar project that is currently being implemented and that follows the same principle of the project TrAZILica. This main objective of this new project *Better integration of asylum seekers with education* is to increase the employability of asylum seekers through the development and implementation of programs for linguistic and cultural integration of asylum seekers, individual mentoring and vocational training programs for simple occupations in the tourism and hospitality sector where there is a labour shortage. All of the above will contribute to their better competitiveness in the labour market, which will influence their successful integration into Croatian society.

The respondent emphasized the importance of including classes of computer literacy to a future project because this seems to be an urgent need that arose through project TrAZILica, and the current project *Better integration of asylum seekers with*.

Best Practice: BEST (Boosting Entrepreneurial Skills as Tool of integration of migrants to labour market)

Partner name: Centre for Peace Studies

Name and position of the respondent: Helena Habdija, Project Manager at Impact Hub Zagreb.

Date of the interview: November 2020.

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner): Impact Hub Zagreb, which is a leading collaborative space, a community of entrepreneurs and innovators with a unique spirit that enables, connects and inspires the current and future generations of changemakers for a better society.

References or documentation about the best practice: The BEST project is a joint endeavour of 8 partners from Austria (Gain&Sustain, FH Joanneum), Slovenia (ZRC SAZU), Croatia (CPS, Impact HUB Zagreb) and Italy (FINN, OIKOS).

General information about the project can be found on its [webpage](#) and [Facebook page](#). Furthermore, within the project, project partners filmed experiences of project participants. You can find these videos [here](#). There is also a [specific video](#) made by Croatian partners.

- Project main page: <https://www.bestofgs.eu/project-best/>
- Project Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/project.BEST.amif/>
- Promotional video for project BEST: <https://youtu.be/WaEWgZf9dIE>
- Promotional video introducing participants from Croatia: https://youtu.be/gK3tSmB_kLo

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Integration of third-country nationals into the labour market, employment of third-country nationals.

Target group(s): Third-country nationals, representatives of institutions, representatives of non-governmental organisations.

Financial background: The project BEST is a project funded by the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund from the European Commission, DG for Migration and Home Affairs, for the integration of the Third Country Nationals, under the priority “Promote swift integration of Third Country Nationals (TCNs) into the labour market

through strengthened cooperation and mobilisation of employers and social and economic partners.”

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): From February 2019 until July 2010.

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The objectives of the BEST project are:

- Promote early and effective integration in the labour market of third-country nationals, by creating effective transnational partnerships with all actors concerned and in particular social and economic partners, employers, public and private employment services and national and local authorities to foster the development of tools, methods, capacity building and exchange of experience;
- Raise awareness about the conditions for early and effective labour market integration of third-country nationals, as well as of its economic and social benefits and mobilise employers and other key actors to become active on this topic.

Mapping the needs (if applicable):

This project was a continuation of previous successful cooperation among project partners that touched upon the topic of integration of third-country nationals into the labour market through project DRIM (Danube Compass).

Detailed description:

BEST project is a joint endeavour of 8 partners from Austria, Slovenia, Croatia and Italy that have the common motivation to improve the effective integration of third-country nationals into the labour market through cooperation between public and private institutions. The BEST project emerged when working on projects that have as main focus economic and social integration of migrants where the need of offering specific strategies to third-country nationals who would like to become self-employed and/or open their own business emerged.

The project developed the pedagogical framework based on non-formal and blended learning methodologies which gave third-country national different skill set that is needed in the world of

entrepreneurship. Project partners implemented social entrepreneurship trainings in each partner-country and established effective cooperation with public key-stakeholders, aiming to facilitate the management of migrant integration and designing a tailored training program with blended learning. Through this project, third-country nationals have a platform on which they can discuss social problems in their communities and identify creative thinking techniques to quickly generate solutions for them. This project allowed third-country nationals to develop the soft skills that every entrepreneur needs; creative thinking, critical thinking, ability to make decisions, and the ability to take initiative. The focus is on the problem and research. Knowing everything about the problem is crucial as it makes it easier to solve. The tools and topics that BEST project covers enables third-country nationals to apply them in solving any problem and developing any business idea, now or in the future.

Migrant entrepreneurs became in the long term crucial for the integration of other migrants into the labour market and they created an important bridge to the global market. Nevertheless, migrant entrepreneurs face additional challenges when starting their enterprises, such as lack of resources and lack of access to information, limited knowledge of the language or complicated administrative procedures. There is also a lack of trust towards the public authorities. The BEST project intends to build a bridge through concrete cooperation activities between different key actors in the integration of TCN in the labour market, as well as those institutions and organizations that can provide the needed support to the entrepreneurs to develop and implement their ideas creating socio-economic value for the EU.

Through BEST courses different profiles of third-country nationals had a chance to meet. All of them were driven with the need to change their situation but to also further help the new society in which they now call home. The BEST project allowed building connections between third-country nationals, public authorities, and non-governmental organizations. Its primary goal was not that all third-country nationals who pass the social entrepreneurship course open their own business but to gain skills necessary to overcome current issues they are facing and possibly give them an opportunity that once in their future they will be able to rely on their business idea and its prosperity. The success of the project lies in its flexibility to adequately re-arrange the social-entrepreneurship courses following the needs of the third-country nationals. The BEST project also allowed representatives of public authorities and other non-governmental organisations to learn the importance of adequate mentorship and see to what extent third-country nationals can help our society if they are given a chance and support.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

This project allowed third-country nationals to develop the soft skills that every entrepreneur needs; creative thinking, critical thinking, ability to make decisions, and the ability to take initiative. It also taught representatives of public authorities and other non-governmental organisations the importance of mentorship.

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

To ensure the success of the project it was important to assure that the pedagogical framework based on non-formal and blended learning methodologies was implemented flexibly, according to the needs of each group of third-country nationals. The great responsibility was put on trainers who weekly worked with third-country nationals, and motivated and guided them throughout the whole process. Furthermore, for the success of the project in Croatian context, it was important to have an organisation that is an expert in the field of social entrepreneurship (Impact Hub) and an organisation that is experienced in working with third-country nationals and can identify struggles with which third-country nationals are struggling in the national context (Centre for Peace Studies Zagreb). Epidemiological circumstances proved that this project can be implemented online if needed.

Why is it the best practice?

This project not only allows entering into the world of social entrepreneurship but allows third-country nationals to gain necessary skills that will help them overcome different problems that they might face while trying to integrate into the labour market. This project also understands the current global situation and recognizes social entrepreneurship as a possible answer to many challenges different societies are facing. It is not only about teaching third-country nationals about the theory of social entrepreneurship, but it is about empowering them, and guiding them through their process of thinking about social issues and finding out different ways to address them. Instead of portraying third-country nationals as passive observers, this project strives to give them a tool for better and easier integration into the labour market, whether it ought to be through their own business or becoming an integral part of some company.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

Implementation of the project in several countries showed that this project is fully transferable to any national context since it gives the skills for the future and offers an innovative approach to addressing the lengthiness of integration into the labour market.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to another context?

This example of best practice is transferable to any context.

Additional notes from the researcher:

The respondent informed us that this current project would be even more successful if it had included both third-country nationals and locals. Social entrepreneurship courses could not only in that scenario be a place for labour market integration, but also an arena for overall social integration. This is something that might be considered if this project should be applied in any other different context.

Best Practice: Projekt Nový začátek (New Beginning - Improvement of Female Migrants)

Partner name: Inbáze z.s.

Name of the best practice: Projekt Nový začátek (New Beginning - Improvement of Female Migrants)

Name and position of the respondent: Alice Mullerová, career counsellor

Date of the interview: August, 2020

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner): Inbáze z.s.

References or documentation about the best practice: List of supported persons (target group migrant women), project documentation, Individual action plan, methodological guidelines for career counsellors

<https://inbaze.cz/pracovni-a-karierni-poradenstvi/>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Career guidance

Target group(s): Migrant women

Financial background: The project is financed by the Operational Programme Employment (ESF)

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): 2017 -2018

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The main goal of the project was to eliminate or mitigate the obstacles faced by migrant women in the process of labour integration and succeeding on the Czech labour market. A complex programme (guidance, motivation, education) has been put forward to achieve this goal. It was fulfilled based on an individual approach to the needs of the clients. More than 300 women from Prague have benefited from this project as they were afforded a plethora of services to help them succeed on the labour market.

The project has been awarded the Award for a Newly Established Service within the National Career Guidance Award contest in the year 2017.

Mapping the needs:

Before the start of the project, a survey and interviews with InBáze clients took place. These were in particular the following obstacles:

1. Social exclusion, ignorance of the new environment, low self - confidence, disqualification, discrimination due to gender, origin, motherhood or cultural difference in roles of men and women;
2. Barriers to entering the labor market (problems with obtaining or extending residence permits, language knowledge, recognition of education achieved, orientation in the field of labor law etc.);
3. Clients sometimes solve barriers to entering the labor market through illegal work, which exposes them to high vulnerabilities.
4. The employment of foreigners is often more difficult for HR professionals, they are not sufficiently oriented to the valid legislation, are not sufficiently informed about the abilities and skills of migrants.

The individual needs of the clients in this project have been identified individually in the first meetings with career consultants. An individual development plan has been compiled with each client.

Detailed description:

The basis of this project was fruitful co-operation of clients with career consultants according to a methodology made during the first period of the project. Individual career guidance was provided to the clients during the whole duration of the project. Its aim was not only mapping the needs but also guidance through individual services and the final evaluation of the goal which was achieved.

An individual development plan has been compiled during the first meeting of a client and a career consultant. Clients could benefit from a plethora of services from this project on the basis of this plan. This was mainly Czech lessons or Soft skills courses such as Communication, Self-development and Self-presentation, Financial literacy, Law and Interview preparation. Clients also had the option of Group guidance, Skills assessment, CH-Q courses, Career talks meetings and the services of a lawyer and a psychologist. Selected participants have been given a free requalification course based on their needs.

About 30 clients have obtained new qualifications as an accountant, tourist guide, social worker etc. The new qualifications enabled clients to get jobs and long-term employment in the labour market.

The self-help group was initiated as a part of the project activities. The group as well as the group meetings were very important for self confidence development of project clients, migrant women. Career counselling services were fully adapted to the needs of migrant clients as well as mentoring programme provided career development opportunities.

Motivational meetings within career talks enabled clients to get acquainted with examples of successful careers from different professions during face-to-face meetings with women living in the Czech Republic and to establish personal contact with them.

More than 300 clients used various services during the two years project.

The participation of clients in the project was finished with a final evaluation of the achieved goal. The project was run for two years and it was finished by the end of financial support.

All services were provided to the clients free of charge. About ten staff members were included in the projects. Mainly career counsellors as well as other experts as a lecturers, psychologist, others and supported staff were involved.

Expected results/benefits for the target group:

Unemployed migrant women living in Prague had the opportunity to gain new knowledge and skills and to develop existing ones during the project and therefore gained a better chance to succeed in the Czech labour market. Clients appreciated advanced Czech language lessons (focused on the labour market topic), which are usually not available to migrants, the option of requalification but also a broad spectrum of education courses, which contributed not only to gaining further knowledge and skills, better orientation in the sociocultural environment of the Czech Republic but especially to further self-knowledge and confidence in job-searching and in the job itself. A number of clients have found employment appropriate for their qualification after the project.

Material required/resources:

Individual development plan, methodical procedure in providing the service

Why is the best practice?

Migrant women are one of the groups most exposed to discrimination on the labour market. It is the case with migrants on/close after maternity leave or with women caring for children or close persons. This combination along with a language barrier creates a great obstacle in entering the labour market.

The services available in the project can be considered „best practice“ mainly in relation to the complexity of the programme including different forms of education and guidance and individual guidance provided by career consultants.

This project, unlike usual practice provided by social services provided by Inbáze z.s., has allowed the provision of complex services tailored for each client individually based on the financial support by the ESF.

Clients have gained new knowledge in the areas of labour law and Czech legislature, financial literacy, CV preparation etc., furthered their knowledge of the Czech language, communication skills and practiced self-presentation and other means of self-development through this project. A part of them also gained new qualifications including better orientation in the conditions of the labour market.

The project contributed to increasing the confidence of the clients and a part of them have found employment during the project.

The project has proved the effectiveness of the selected means, contributed to faster integration of the clients and proved the effectiveness of the public funds spent towards this goal.

The project also contributed to the advancement of equal opportunities for the group of migrant women.

Last, but not least, this project contributed to the professionalization of career guidance services provided by InBáze.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

The above mentioned good practice can be transferred to other countries with similar labour market conditions and similar characteristics of migrants (education, language skills, motivation, etc.). It is advised to use the entire concept of the programme based on the complexity and individual approach to clients. The condition of a successful transfer is also ensuring that the programme is financed as a whole for at least half a year.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

The transferability depends mainly on the character of the target group and its motivation to be integrated in the given country. The group should be similar to the one involved in this project in regards to education, language skills, motivation, the willingness to integrate and other factors considering the fact that this programme has been designed according to the needs of the target group (i.e. highly motivated female migrants originating mainly from former USSR countries with secondary or higher education and at least a basic knowledge of the Czech language).

Best Practice: Fair Food Club

Partner name: Inbáze z.s

Name of the best practice: Fair Food Club

Name and position of the respondent: Lela (anonym respondent)

Date of the interview: October 20, 2020

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner):

Fair Food Club s.r.o.

References or documentation about the best practice:

<https://www.fairfoodclub.cz/>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Catering, food service, gastronomy

Target group(s): Entrepreneurs

Financial background: Private business

Dates of the best practice (if applicable):

In business since 2014

LABOUR MARKET
INTEGRATION OF
THIRD-COUNTRY
NATIONALS
IN CROATIA, THE
CZECH REPUBLIC,
HUNGARY AND
SLOVAKIA

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

A successful business project of a migrant woman who in the beginning of her stay in the Czech Republic received support in the Ethnocatering project run by InBáze z.s. Later with the help of the acquired knowledge and skills she started her own business. She now has migrant and Czech employees and is trying to return the help she received - she combines entrepreneurial skills, leadership and a desire to help.

Lela stated in the interview: „I wanted my own business, even though I had no experience in this regard, but I wanted to do something with and for people. My work experience from the social business Ethnocatering was a great help as it allowed me to try out many things in a safe environment.“

Mapping the needs:

This business project started on the basis of the university cafeteria offer to operate on its premises. They were interested in the services provided by Ethnocatering.

Lela stated in the interview: *„I wanted my own business, even though I had no experience in this regard, but I wanted to do something with and for people. My work experience from the social business Ethnocatering was a great help as it allowed me to try out many things in a safe environment.“*

Detailed description:

A young woman, by the name of Lela, came to the Czech Republic from Georgia in 2003 as an asylum seeker. She worked in a social catering business „Ethnocatering“ in Prague for 9 years, first as an ordinary employee and then as a manager for 7 years. She has used this experience in gastronomy and catering to open her own university buffet in Prague in the year 2014, which is still successfully in business with her at the helm.

Fair Food Club s.r.o.. provides the possibility of fair earnings and self-realization for women in difficult life situations (eg migrant women or single mothers). In cooperation with the social enterprise Ethnocatering, they give the possibility of employment and fair work to migrant women - clients of the InBáze community center.

In cooperation with the Prague organization Rytmus in creating jobs for people with disabilities.

This company has been helping since 2014 to change the form of catering.

„We bring honest, fresh and healthy food to the campus and catering. Our varied menus are based on ethnic cuisines and are prepared on the principles of healthy nutrition (meat, vegetarian, vegan, gluten-free). We use fresh ingredients from proven sources - whether it's meat, vegetables, rice or herbs“.

Together with Lela, 5 people are employed in this cafeteria, with occasional part – time workers (there are seasonal changes the number of customers is changing, but in a peak of the season is around 200). They sell food from the Armenian, Georgian, Indian and Czech cuisine.

Expected results/benefits for the target group:

The buffet operates with great success and it represents a successful, sustainable business model. There are two target groups

in this case - Lela and other migrants entering the labour market, trying to succeed in a private business, and, at the same time, recent employees working in Fair Food Club (migrants, Czech, with special needs) in a friendly environment, which Lela creates for them.

„The most important part to me are the people, the satisfied customers, who come back. I'm happy when they compliment us on the food, but at the same time it's important to me to help others, especially foreign women, who have very little options in a foreign environment and have got little to no work experience.“ says Lela.

Material required/resources:

The university provided equipment. Lela received a loan and a sponsorship gifts and also invested her savings in starting a business.

Lela says: *„It is definitely important to have a clear vision and at least a basic business plan, which says how much things will cost and contains a realistic estimate of how much the business will bring in, when will the costs be covered and when will the business become profitable. It is important to think of the customers, to make sure they're satisfied and to try and figure out what they desire. It's also important to make sure your employees are satisfied and of course to be prepared to work hard. In the beginning we did everything with my friend, my business partner, on our own. Later, we could afford a cook, a cleaning woman, etc. I believe this is how it works everywhere in the world and you can start anywhere.“*

Why is the best practice?

The buffet has been in business since the year 2014 and it's an example of a successful enterprise, started by a young female foreigner in Prague. We have chosen this best practice because it provides an example of how supporting a migrant woman at the beginning of her stay, together with her own effort, can lead to successful self-employment. The work in social enterprise – Etnocatering – run by InBáze z.s. gave her the necessary background for the realization of her own professional ambitions.

Lela says: *„I had no experience, I was 27 years old, I've never worked, I had two little children and I didn't speak the language. The experience in Etnocatering helped me, and the fact that it was known in Prague made it possible for me to receive an offer from the university to start my own buffet.“*

„It is important, as an example of good practice, that I had the option to try out many things in the safe environment of Etnocatering and I

have therefore avoided many mistakes in my own business. I consider it to be very important to have a „testing ground“ such as this. I've also had the option to get to know the conditions of the gastronomy industry before I started doing business“ adds Lela.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

We have chosen this example because it represents a combination of different, complex forms of assistance - the initial – very practical support for migrants in the beginning of their stay with further skills training, networking, mentoring and other support, according to individual needs.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

From our point of view this best practice could be transferable quite well to other context.

Best Practice: Sirius festival of(f) work

Partner name: Inbáze z.s.

Name of the best practice: Sirius festival of(f) work

Name and position of the respondent: Janowska Justyna, project coordinator

Date of the interview: October, 2020

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner):

The Multicultural Center Prague (MKC Prague) is a non-profit organisation engaged in the pursuit of educational and research activities in the fields of international migration, social inclusion of Roma, and global development. Founded in 1999, they have strived for a Czech society based on respect for human rights, political equality, and intercultural competence and understanding.

<https://mkc.cz/en/about>

References or documentation about the best practice:

Web page of the Sirius project <https://www.sirius-project.eu/>

Web page of the festival (part of the Sirius Project):

<https://www.kampushybernska.cz/2019/04/19/4551/>

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Labour migration

Target group(s): Migrants, refugees, asylum seekers

Financial background: European Union, Horizon 2018 - 2020 Research

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): 2019

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

Sirius festival of(f) work was held as a part of the project SIRIUS: Skills and Integration of Migrants, Refugees and Asylum Seekers in European Labour Market.

The organizer wanted to design a program based on the mix of culture and practicality, so they decided to combine presentations with workshops. The cultural program provided the rest and

relaxation. They also wanted to attract Czechs and foreigners to connect two different “worlds”.

Mapping the needs (if applicable):

The world of work and labour is changing rapidly. We spend more than a third of our lives in employment and every fifth person working in Prague is foreign. This is why the Multicultural Centre Prague wanted to organize the Sirius festival of(f) work. Through the festival they wanted to draw attention to this important topic in a playful and yet practical manner.

The organizers wanted to create a space that connects the residents of the metropolis irrespective of where they come from. The topic of "work" is a very suitable subject to focus on as it is highly relevant to all.

Detailed description:

Sirius festival of(f) work was held as a part of the ongoing project SIRIUS. Sirius project has three main objectives:

1. To provide systematic evidence on post-2014 migrants, refugees and asylum applicants especially women and young people and their potential for labour market employment and, more broadly, social integration.
2. To advance knowledge on the complexity of labour market integration for post-2014 migrants, refugees and asylum applicants, and to explore their integration potential by looking into their spatial distribution (in relation to the distribution of labour demand across the labour market), while taking into account labour market characteristics and needs in different country and socio-economic contexts.
3. To advance a theoretical framework for an inclusive integration agenda, outlining an optimal mix of policy pathways for labour market integration including concrete steps that Member States and other European countries along with the EU can take to ensure that migrant-integration policies and the broader system of workforce-development, training, and employment programmes support new arrivals' access to decent work opportunities and working conditions.

SIRIUS has a mixed methods approach and innovative dissemination plan involving online priority action networks, film essays, festival, job fair and an applied game along with scientific and policy dialogue workshops and conferences.

The program combined learning and culture - practical workshops to help improve labor market orientation - Diversity management workshop, workshop How to successfully enter the labour market, together with individual career counselling and CV photo corner. Round table with trade union representatives was focused on the Labour self - defence skills and non violent communication. with culture was also connected with labor market thematic - film projections, exhibition, concert together with a meeting place.

The festival's website also had Russian, Ukrainian and English language versions including events on Facebook. Workshops were held in the Czech language, but the language skills of the participants were taken into account. It was enough to have knowledge of Czech at the A2 / B1 level.

Expected results/benefits for the target group(s):

The aim of the Sirius festival of(f) work was to help migrant workers better navigate the job market, to boost their self esteem, deepen knowledge and provide them with a wider range of skills that are required to find a job.

Material required/resources (human, technical and other conditions to implement the best practice):

Material resources: space, infographics, technical equipment etc..

Staff: 3 persons – organization, communication, PR etc.

Why is it the best practice?

Sirius festival of(f) work was a unique combination of culture and practicality. It was close to the place where people live, easy to reach for all. The first goal – education was fulfilled – there was a wide offer of activities. The second goal – connecting people from different backgrounds – was more difficult to fulfil - overall, there were mostly foreigners on workshops, but they formed a minority on other activities (labor law minimum etc.). Also - other people came to specific activities.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

Things where language is not so much needed - expression through music, movement, theater, etc.

Specific topic - labor law, because it applies to everyone, even Czech participants

Educational activities focused on work.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

Organization of such an event is financially demanding, here it was part of a big project which ensured enough resources.

Best Practice: Supporting migrants in entering the labour market in Prague

Partner name: Inbáze z.s.

Name and position of the respondent: Alexandr Zpěvák

Date of the interview: August 20, 2020

Institution which developed the best practice (if different from the partner):

References or documentation about the best practice:

[Podpora migrantům při vstupu na trhu práce v Praze - InBáze, z. s. \(inbaze.cz\)](https://inbaze.cz)

Field of the best practice (choose all appropriate fields): Education, job and entrepreneurship counseling

Target group(s): Migrants living in Prague

Financial background: The project was financed from the Operational Programme Prague – Adaptability (ESF)

Dates of the best practice (if applicable): 2013 -2015

DESCRIPTION OF THE BEST PRACTICE

General objective:

The objective of this project was to support migrants living in Prague in facilitating their access to the labour market, starting a business and to support their integration. The objective was achieved by realising 4 key activities including career guidance, business guidance, internship in a social business and supporting services (babysitting, psychotherapy etc.)

Mapping the needs:

Mapping the needs of clients was done before initiating the project and then particular needs have been specified within labour guidance.

Detailed description:

The project was realised in two main areas according to the needs of the participating clients. One part was focused on guidance and the support of succeeding in the labour market and the other was focused on business through a „How to be an entrepreneur in the Czech Republic“ course. Clients in both areas had the option to participate in an internship in the social business of the applicant – Etnocatering. Clients also had available variety of supporting activities such as babysitting, individual tutoring, support groups for women and psychotherapy.

Clients were also provided with social counselling service, which were greatly appreciated by clients as helping them in their difficult situation. These were mostly assistance (including assistance with state authorities) in the handling of state social benefits as well as material need benefit, counselling focused on housing and housing search, medical assistance etc.

The job counsellors provided advice regularly 5 times a week in the morning and afternoon so that working people could also benefit from these services. It was also possible to arrange an individual consultation outside these hours. Mothers with children had the opportunity to use the children´s corner and babysitting service.

69 clients were supported in the project and 10 employees participated in the fulfilment of the project objectives.

Expected results/benefits for the target group:

Migrants from Ukraine, Russia, Algeria, Turkmenistan, Macedonia, Indonesia, Bosnia and other countries were involved in the project. During the project a nostrification of diplomas for 6 clients took place, along with 10 requalification courses, 9 clients entered into an employment contract, 3 clients started their own business and 13 business plans have been drawn up.

Material required/resources:

Materials for the „How to be an entrepreneur in the Czech Republic“ course.

[Podpora migrantům při vstupu na trhu práce v Praze - InBáze, z. s. \(inbaze.cz\)](http://inbaze.cz).

Why is the best practice?

The fact that during this project 9 clients concluded an employment contract and started working and 3 clients started their own business can be considered „best practice“ as it proves the project is appropriate in regards to real needs of the clients but also to the Czech labour market and entrepreneurship conditions.

Supporting activities such as babysitting, women support groups and others have contributed to the success of the project to a large extent.

The clients have given praise to the internships in the applicant's own social business Etnocatering, where the participants have been given a chance to improve their skills in a real environment and to understand the reality of entrepreneurship.

Which elements of the best practice are transferable?

The above mentioned „best practice“ can be transferred to other countries with similar labour market conditions and characteristics of the migrants (education, language skills, etc.). It is appropriate to use the above mentioned concept of a programme based on the option of requalification and the individual approach of career guidance including assistance in the process of job seeking all the way to entering into an employment contract. The condition of a successful transfer of this good practice is also ensuring sufficient long-term financing of the project.

Which elements of the best practice are impossible to transfer to other context?

The internships took place right in applicants' own social enterprise. In case that other organization does not have appropriate facilities, it is not easy to transfer this element – to ensure the practical training.

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